

Haptic Gloves (SM-EXO) for Multi-Users in Pick-and-Place Collaborative Robot Simulated Environment

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Abstract

The use of collaborative pick-and-place robots has been gaining popularity in recent years, given their ability to work alongside humans in various industrial and manufacturing environments. The use of smart wearables as the Industrial Internet of Wearable Things (IIoWT), to facilitate efficiency of such environments is receiving vast attention. In this article, we present the development of a novel smart glove (SM-EXO) integrated with the RobotStudio simulation software for use in a multi-user pick-and-place collaborative robot-simulated environment. The proposed smart glove uses an intuitive force-feedback concept to provide users with a sense of constraint while moving their fingers, thus giving them a more organic feeling. A series of experiments were conducted in the simulated environment pairing the SM-EXO with several robotic arms to evaluate the feasibility and repeatability of the concept. Our results show that the SM-EXO effectively improves human control over the robotic arm in the simulated environment. These results can be directly translated into the real environment as well as AR/VR environments for training purposes. To facilitate intelligent learning and prediction of human intentions, we propose a finger-based gesture understanding approach using Shape Memory Alloy wires and displacement sensors embedded in the smart glove. This study provides a foundation for further research in Industry 4.0, with future directions and applications domains discussed with a focus on two specific use cases. The first use case is worker safety and convenience in hazardous environments in Industry 4.0. The second is based on rehabilitation using SM-EXO controlled simulated set of tasks.

Keywords: Shape Memory Alloy, Multi-User Collaboration, Smart Gloves, Human-Computer Interaction, AR-VR Technology

1 Introduction

The term "Industry 4.0," also known as the fourth industrial revolution, originated from the high-tech strategy of the German federal government in 2011. Industry 4.0 aims to utilize the internet, digital technologies, and quantum sciences to advance autonomous and intelligent cyber-physical systems. As Industry 4.0 continues to develop, it can be defined as the integration of cyber-physical systems, cloud technology, the Internet of Things, and the Internet of Services, interacting with humans in real-time to maximize value creation. By combining the physical and virtual worlds, interoperability, advanced artificial intelligence, and autonomy will become integral parts of this new industrial era [Hwang, 2016]. Integration of smart wearables as a part of the Industrial Internet of Wearable Things (IIoWT) has further revolutionised the way we perceive modern manufacturing. The major focus of these wearables is on worker safety and data collation.

Smart wearables have become an increasingly popular technology in many industries due to their ability to enhance efficiency, safety, and productivity. In manufacturing, smart wearables such as smart glasses and headsets can provide workers with hands-free access to real-time data, allowing them to complete tasks more efficiently and with greater accuracy. In healthcare, wearables can track vital signs and provide early detection of potential health issues for patients, as well as provide health professionals with remote access to patient data. Smart wearables are also being used in logistics and warehousing, where they can provide workers with

real-time inventory information, route optimization, and enhanced safety features. With the ability to provide a wealth of information in real-time, smart wearables are poised to revolutionize many industries, providing workers with valuable insights and enabling them to make better-informed decisions [Srivastava et al., 2022a].

Industrial wearables can be categorized into four major groups, namely Monitoring, Supporting, Training, and Tracking. The Monitoring category is not limited to analyzing the vital signs of workers but also includes monitoring the workplace's environmental conditions. Supporting wearables not only augments the physical abilities of workers through exoskeletons but also enables communication among them. Wearables that monitor the accuracy of a worker's actions and provide detailed reports, such as those utilizing the biomechanical analysis to determine proper posture, fall under the Training category. Lastly, Tracking wearables are responsible for keeping tabs on the location of workers and machinery, providing a comprehensive overview of the production line for safer worker-machine interactions [Svertoka et al., 2021].

Simulated environments play a crucial role when working with industrial robots. These virtual environments offer a valuable testing ground for the system under development, allowing workers to assess its performance and functionality before deploying it in a physical cell. By simulating real-world conditions and scenarios, such as collision detection, path planning, and task execution, engineers can identify potential issues, optimize robot behaviour, and validate the system's overall design. Simulated environments not only save time and resources but also contribute to a safer working environment for the initial testing phase, as they eliminate the risk of accidents or damage to physical equipment [Oyekan et al., 2019]. Additionally, simulated environments enable the reuse of code, making it easier to transfer and apply algorithms and programs from the virtual environment to the physical robot, thereby streamlining the development process and enhancing efficiency [Al-Ahmari et al., 2016]. RobotStudio, the official platform for working with ABB industrial robots, offers a wide range of tools to develop and test projects in both the physical and digital layers of the system. Among these tools, RobotStudio includes its native programming language (RAPID), which is capable of reading and writing data from/to other programming languages using TCP/IP protocols. This feature allows for the development of more complex applications beyond the RAPID language, where only the final results, such as a robot target, need to be sent.

As human-robot collaboration becomes more commonplace, there is an increasing demand for safe, efficient, and cost-effective solutions. One such solution is the development of smart gloves, which are equipped with sensors that can accurately capture and analyze data on the wearer's movements. This technology holds great potential for improving workplace safety, productivity, and overall efficiency. However, effective collaboration between humans and robots through smart gloves still requires significant improvements. This study presents an innovative approach to real-time human-robot interaction in collaborative tasks through the development of an Arduino-embedded and ROS-compatible smart glove system. The approach is implemented using RAPID programming in RobotStudio, with three baseline gestures from thumb, index, and middle finger, used alongside appended labels and corresponding sensor data. Real-world validation of the proposed system and approach shows potential applications in Industry 4.0, healthcare, and daily assistance for rehabilitation. The future applications and research scope in this field are vast, especially using the same concept for user training purposes in AR and VR environments, which will be the further directions in this research.

2 Shape Memory Alloy-based Exoskeleton (SM-EXO)

The selection of material was a critical aspect of designing the glove. To ensure that the glove could be used for extended periods, particularly by children, it was essential to select a soft material, preferably fabric, suitable for everyday use. Therefore, the prototype of the glove is designed with an external attachment of SMA wire and sensors (SM-EXO) that can be attached to any glove. This eliminates the need to design multiple gloves based on the size and shape of the hand. The external mechanism fits the fingers using ring-like 3D printed attachments, serving as guides for the SMA wires and attachment mechanisms for any glove. The ring's size can be adjusted based on the finger's diameter. The SMA wires pass through these rings and are fixed at one end, while linear position sensors are attached to the other end. The position sensors are fixed to the glove using industrial Velcro tapes, allowing the sensor's location to be changed based on the subject's hand size and

Figure 1: Design and mechanism of the Smart Glove and Proof-of-concept. (a) Computer-Aided Design of the SM-EXO, Position Rings, and Tubing for the SMA routing [Srivastava et al., 2022b]. (b) Detailed view of the first SM-EXO prototype [Srivastava et al., 2022c].

dimension. Finally, the glove's base is attached with a Velcro strip, which controls the glove's diameter and enables it to be worn by subjects of any age, size, or gender. Figure 2 depicts the Computer-Aided Design of the glove made in Autodesk Fusion 360, and the complete design of the glove is shown in Figure 2, with wire routing and Velcro strips. The user-centric design of the glove is unique as it offers variable geometry. As the SM-EXO attachment on the glove is easily detachable, users can further customize the glove design based on their preferences and weather conditions. Therefore, the proposed modular SM-EXO design is not only innovative as a smart glove concept, but its customizable potential sets it apart from any state-of-the-art glove. The advantages of the proposed design over available gloves are discussed in detail in the Conclusions and Table 1.

2.1 Design and Mechanism

Before finalizing the SMA wire routing method for the glove, various designs were proposed and discussed. One idea involved embedding the wires within a custom-designed glove, while another was to pass the wire through tubing attached externally to the glove from the tip of the finger to the base of the finger. Ultimately, the current design was chosen, which involves passing the wire through 3D printed self-adjustable rings. Although the embedded wire-sensor design is being considered for advanced phases of the concept, the proposed prototype design is deemed a seamless, lightweight, and hassle-free alternative to the tubing design. It significantly reduces the complexity, material requirement, and weight of the glove. Additionally, the rings' variable diameter ensures the firm grip of the SM-EXO attachment to the glove, acting as an SMA wire guide between the fixed and potentiometer-connected ends. The rings are designed with holes corresponding to the 0.8 mm diameter of the NiTiNOL wire used, securing and allowing free movement of the wire through them. Figure 1 illustrates the fixed end of the wire and the ring with tubing attachment for SMA wire passing and movement.

The KTP Linear Position Sensor with spring feedback is used to attach the SMA wires. These sensors measure the displacement of the wires when the fingers move and generate a voltage response. The open hand

position is considered as the reference point for this measurement, and the bending of the fingers results in a series of voltage responses that vary depending on the angle of bending. The KTP linear position sensors employed in this study exhibit a high degree of repeatability, with a tolerance range of ± 0.0127 , and are engineered for use in joystick or robotics applications with high shock and vibration resistance. Moreover, the sensor features an integral slider, spring return design, infinite high resolution, and an operating life of 2 million cycles. The position sensors capture the displacement data of the SMA wire as the fingers move and transmit it to a computer for storage and processing. The processed data is then utilized as actuation signals for the simulated environment. The authors have discussed the working of the glove and the proof-of-concept in more detail in their previous works [Srivastava et al., 2022b], [Srivastava et al., 2022c].

3 RobotStudio Simulated Environment

RobotStudio is a powerful software tool developed by ABB Robotics for designing, simulating, and programming industrial robots. It provides a virtual environment for testing and optimizing robot programs before they are implemented in real-world applications. RobotStudio includes features such as robot calibration, collision detection, and path planning, making it an essential tool for robot system integration and programming. It supports a wide range of robot models and applications, and its user-friendly interface makes it accessible to both novice and expert users. It is a powerful tool used by robotics engineers, automation experts, and manufacturing professionals to create, simulate, and optimize robot systems. With RobotStudio, users can create a virtual model of a robot and its surroundings, allowing them to test the robot's movements and functions before deploying it on the shop floor. The software also allows for offline programming (RAPID), where users can program the robot without needing to connect it to the actual hardware, saving time and reducing downtime. Additionally, RobotStudio supports a wide range of robot models and configurations, making it a versatile tool for various industrial applications [Connolly, 2009].

RAPID is a high-level programming language that is used to control industrial robots, particularly those manufactured by ABB. It was developed by ABB Robotics in the 1990s to provide a powerful and flexible programming interface for their robots. RAPID stands for "Robot Application Programming Interface for Developers," and it is designed to be easy to use, even for those with little or no programming experience. RAPID is a structured programming language that uses a combination of keywords, variables, and functions to define the robot's movements and actions. It allows programmers to control the robot's movements in three-dimensional space, as well as to interact with sensors and other external devices. RAPID programs can be written offline and then uploaded to the robot's controller, or they can be created and edited directly on the robot itself. One of the key advantages of RAPID is its flexibility. It allows programmers to create complex programs that can be easily modified and adapted to changing production needs. It also provides a wide range of built-in functions for common robotic tasks, such as path planning, collision detection, and error handling. This makes it easier and faster to develop new robotic applications, even for those without extensive programming experience [Holubek et al., 2014].

3.1 Integrating SM-EXO

The smart glove is able to send data from the microcontroller to the computer via Bluetooth, WiFi, or Serial Connection. For the sake of this article, we connected the glove to the computer using a serial connection. The voltage signal generated from the bending of the fingers is received and identified using Python and is sent to the RobotStudio simulation environment using the RAPID programming language. We define the voltage limits from the position sensor between 0 and 1. Hence, 0 corresponds to no voltage, whereas 1 represents the highest voltage which is 5V. This allows us to define the multiple combinations of the movement of the x-y-z axis of the end effector on the robotic arm. Table 1 shows the truth table for the axis movements and the corresponding fingers that are causing the movement. We have, furthermore, defined the coordinates of the movement of the end effector between (0,0,0) and (1,1,1) locations on the x, y, and z axis respectively.

Figure 2: The flow architecture of the Cyber-Physical system in the glove-robot simulated environment.

Table 1: Truth Table for the movement configurations of the end-effector based on the finger movement.

X	Y	Z	Output (Movement)	Finger
0	0	0	0	None
0	0	1	1	Middle
0	1	0	1	Index
0	1	1	1	Index and Middle
1	0	0	1	Thumb
1	0	1	1	Thumb and Middle
1	1	1	1	All three

4 Multi-Users Collaborative Concept

Multiuser collaborative robots, also known as cobots, are designed to work alongside humans in a shared workspace. Unlike traditional industrial robots that are usually confined to a fenced-off area, cobots are equipped with advanced sensors and algorithms that allow them to operate safely around humans. One of the key advantages of multiuser collaborative robots is their ability to work in a team with human workers. Cobots can assist humans in tasks that require precision, strength, and speed, thereby reducing the workload and improving productivity. Additionally, cobots can also take on repetitive or hazardous tasks, freeing up human workers to focus on more complex or creative tasks. Another advantage of cobots is their flexibility and ease of use. Many cobots are designed to be programmed by non-experts, using intuitive interfaces or even by physically moving the robot arm to teach it a new task. This makes it easier for workers to adapt to new tasks and reduces the need for specialized programming skills. Overall, multiuser collaborative robots have the potential to transform manufacturing and other industries by enabling a more efficient, safe, and flexible way of working [Rodriguez-Guerra et al., 2021].

Use Case

Several robots in a manufacturing assembly unit work together in a shared workspace to accomplish different tasks, such as stud welding or spot welding a car body in the automotive industry's body-in-white process. Figure 1 demonstrates how four cooperative robots operate together in an assembly station. Efficient robot operations demand that the robots complete their tasks in the shortest possible time while preventing collisions with each other. Consequently, identifying a collision-free path for multiple robots to finish their allotted tasks is critical. This is a vital factor from the operator's standpoint [Xin et al., 2020].

Figure 3: Demo from RobotStudio showing a Multi-Robot collaborative setup

In this Use Case, we discuss integrating two smart gloves, individually for each hand, with the multi-robot collaborative system. While one hand controls the robotic arm handling the fragile/hazardous on one conveyor belt and puts it on another, the other glove controls another arm for another pick-and-place action. The application is limited, however, to robotic grippers with 3-finger grips.

The process begins with the user putting on the control glove and establishing a connection with the robots. In this case, there are two steps of communication, i.e., the first is between the glove and Python script and the second is between Python script and RAPID script. For the first one, it's being used a serial communication for reading data from the glove and send it to the Python script. For the second, it's being used a TCP/IP protocol to establish the connection between the Python and RAPID scripts. After the connection is establish, the user has a series of predefined finger movements that allows them to control the robot. As mentioned before, each robot is controlled by one of the gloves, so that all the control gestures are the same for both. The user needs to close and open the fingers twice to enter in the control mode. After entering in the control mode, the user can move their fingers as explained in the section 3.1 to move the robot to the target position. The user can also exit the control mode by closing and opening the fingers twice again. In this way, it is possible move their hands freely when out of the control mode. In this application we focus on the manipulation of fragile/hazardous elements, however, it might be applied in any product manipulation task.

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